

PARENTAL FACTORS RELATED TO STUDENTS' SELF-CONCEPT AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMID COVID-19 AND DISTANCE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Parental factors impact students' self-concept and academic performance during the pandemic. Thus, this study determined the students' self-concept and academic performance and the parental factors related to it. The research design was descriptive-correlational, and 500 nonrandom college students in West Philippines participated in the study. Researcher-made instruments were used, which were subjected to reliability and validity evaluation. Data were collected online from June 2021 to July 2022 and were analyzed using descriptive (frequency counts and percentage) and inferential statistics (Spearman correlation). Results revealed a positive self-concept and satisfactory academic performance among the students. Besides, parental factors such as educational attainment and school/classroom involvement are significantly related to self-concept and academic performance. Further, self-concept is significantly associated with academic performance. This shows that some parental factors are vital in developing the student's self-beliefs and supporting their studies and academic endeavors amid the COVID-19 pandemic. Future studies may consider more factors related to academic achievement and self-concept. Other researchers may find the mediation or moderation effect of self-concept between parental factors and students' scholastic achievement.

Keywords: academic performance, COVID-19 pandemic, distance learning, higher education, parental factors, self-concept

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INTRODUCTION

Parental factors play a significant role in students' self-concept because they contribute to developing their personalities. The upbringing of the parents results in the development of their offspring. As a result, parents should know what is suitable for their children's development since their surroundings reveal who they are. When parents have a positive relationship with their children, it helps them develop a positive self-concept. Parental involvement was instrumental during the pandemic (Agayon et al., 2022; Bacomo et al., 2022; Valoroso et al., 2022). Consequently, students perform better and higher in their academic performance, knowing that their parents value what they do in school. Parents with higher general educational aspirations have children with higher academic self-concept. As one of their fundamental rights, children are provided by their parents with the necessary support and guidance, which are essential in building one's self-concept and academics.

Parental factors are relatively influential to self-concept as well as academic performance. High predictability and consistency across countries show that parental expectations affect students' achievement and self-concepts (Neuenschwander et al., 2007). Parental factors have a constant and favorable effect on academic achievement and self-concept (Chohan & Khan, 2010). Due to the benefits to student academic success, parental involvement has elevated importance in schools (Gonzalez-Pienda, 2002). Besides, parental involvement benefits children not so much through direct skill development as it does through a more subtle influence on their self-concept (De Apodaca et al., 2015). Parents facilitate their children to have confident perspectives and moral beliefs, creating a positive self-concept beneficial for their academic endeavors. Since parental factors influence scholastic performance (De Apodaca et al., 2015) and self-concept predicts their academic performance (Sanchez & Roda, 2003), one may say that an interrelationship between these three variables exists.

Parental factors are to be explored, given that the students have their parents as their teachers and classmates at home. Though school mobility was banned, the students interacted socially with their parents. Zhan and Mei (2013) stressed that distance learning environments had a more substantial impact on students' learning achievement and satisfaction than face-to-face settings did. This event can fundamentally influence students' good self-concept. Self-concept is based on one's experience and environment (Kang & Wu, 2022). Besides, it clearly defines who he is and what he can accomplish independently. As a result, his personality is reflected in whatever he believes about himself. Thus, the action is based on his perception of himself. Self-concept can explain how students perform in school. However, studies have contrasting results about the relationship of self-concept with academic performance. For Ghazvini (2011), self-concept predicts students' academic performance, but Laryea et al. (2014) have different findings.

The incidence of COVID-19 and restrictions on physical classroom instruction have forced distance learning, either online or modular (Agayon et al., 2022; Bacomo et al., 2022; Hamora et al., 2022; Zakaria). This shift in the educational system has challenged parental roles and their child's academic performance. Parental roles and students' academic performance during the pandemic have been explored (Bonilla et al., 2022; Carbonilla et al., 2022; Valoroso et al., 2022), yet no studies have related these variables to the self-concept of college students. Thus, the study was conducted to gauge these gaps and contribute new knowledge to educational research. This study will be relevant in addressing students' poor academic performance and declining sense of self-concept due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The data will serve as a basis for designing intervention programs and action research to lighten the concerns related to distance learning. Also, parents will be informed about how their background can influence their children's academic standing and self-concept.

Objectives of the Study

The study determined the parental factors related to college students' self-concept and academic performance amid distance learning brought about by the pandemic. Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. determine the parental factors in terms of number of children, marital status, monthly income, educational attainment, and school/classroom involvement;
2. define the self-concept of the students, whether positive or negative;
3. describe the academic performance of the students;
4. ascertain if a statistical relationship exists between the parental factors with the student's self-concept and academic performance; and
5. verify if a statistical relationship occurs between the self-concept of the students with their academic performance.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative, particularly a descriptive-correlational research design to determine the parental factors affecting the self-concept and academic performance of the students concerning distance learning. The descriptive-correlational approach categorizes and relates quantitative variables (Magulod et al., 2021). The descriptive phase describes the participants' self-concept and academic performance with the parental factors that may influence these variables, and the correlation phase determines the relationship among these variables. Figure 1 shows the research paradigm showing the relationship among variables.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

Participants and Sampling Technique

The study participants were 500 second- and third-year college students from different public and private universities in the West Philippines. Initially, 511 students were chosen but were trimmed down to 500 to ensure that the data to be reported was valid. They were chosen through availability sampling, where only those who could access the link were able to provide data pertinent to the study objectives. The students' participation was voluntary, and they had the right to refuse participation. Besides, the participants were oriented toward the purpose of the research and the collected data before they could provide their responses through Google Forms. The students must provide their informed consent before filling out and submitting the form.

Data Gathering Procedure and Instruments

Upon approval from the school authorities, the researchers prepared a Google Form that consisted of three parts. Part I deals with the parental factors (regarding the number of children, marital status, monthly income, educational attainment, and school/classroom involvement). Part II determined the

students' self-concept. Positive (e.g., *I am happy with where I am right now.*) and negative statements (e.g., *I changed my mind a lot.*) were used (Appendix I). Reliability of the research tools through test-retest was established, obtaining a correlation coefficient of .89 (Part I), .85 (Part II), and .86 (Part III). These coefficients indicate the reliability and usability of the prepared instruments. Validation was obtained from three external experts, and the researchers followed their recommendations to improve the instruments. Data were collected online from June 2021 to July 2022, and this is to ensure a large sample size while ensuring health and safety protocols during data gathering. The names and emails of the participants were not gathered to warrant anonymity.

Data Analysis

The data gathered were treated through descriptive and inferential analysis. Data screening from 511 responses was conducted, trimming the valid responses to 500. Frequency count and percentage were applied to define the parental factors, self-concept, and academic performance. Meanwhile, Spearman correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the parental factors with the self-concept of the college students with their academic rating and the relationship between the self-concept of the college students with their academic rating. The correlational analysis was conducted at a 95 percent confidence level. Microsoft Excel and Jamovi software were used to facilitate the analysis, as per Pentang (2021).

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Research Findings

Parental Factors

The parental factors that may be related to the student's self-concept and academic performance were determined through the parent's profile regarding the number of children, marital status, monthly income, educational attainment, and school/classroom involvement (Table 1). There were more parents (44.6%) who had three to four offspring, and the majority were living together (75.2%), belonging to the poor socioeconomic class (61.4%), attended high school (51%), and occasionally involved in school/classroom activities (55.6%). These factors show ramifications in the parent's role as new normal teachers and facilitators to their children.

Table 1. Parental Factors

Parent's Profile	Frequency (n=500)	Percentage (%)
Number of Children		
1 to 2	146	29.2
3 to 4	223	44.6
5 or greater	131	26.2
Relationship Status		
Living Together	376	75.2
Living Apart or Separated	36	7.2
Widow/er or Solo Parent	88	17.6
Parents Monthly Income (Socioeconomic Class)		
₱12,082 and below (Poor)	307	61.4
₱12,083 to ₱24,164 (Low-income class, but not poor)	158	31.6
₱24,165 to ₱48,328 (Lower middle-income class)	35	7.0
Parents' Educational Attainment		
Elementary Level	175	35.0
High School Level	255	51.0
College Level	70	14.0
School/Classroom Involvement		
Highly Involved	112	22.4
Occasionally Involved	278	55.6
Not Involved	110	22.0

Students' Self-concept

The students' self-concepts were described as positive and negative (Table 2), based on their agreement with the statements presented (Appendix A). The students have a positive self-concept (57.6%), which shows their optimistic self-beliefs amid the pandemic and distance learning.

Table 2. Students' Self-concept

Self-Concept	Frequency (n=500)	Percentage (%)
Positive Self-concept	288	57.6
Negative Self-concept	212	42.4

Students' Academic Performance

The academic performance of the college students was described using their general weighted average (Table 3), ranging from 1.0 (highest possible grade) to 5.0 (lowest possible grade). This was based on the grading system adopted by most universities. The majority (53%) of the students have shown satisfactory academic performance. This means that the students could meet the minimum requirements for the course despite the barriers made by the pandemic and the new learning modality.

Table 3. Students' Academic Performance

Rating	Frequency (n=500)	Percentage (%)
Outstanding (1.00-1.49)	28	5.6
Very Satisfactory (1.50-1.99)	144	28.8
Satisfactory (2.00-2.49)	265	53.0
Unsatisfactory (2.50-3.00)	63	12.6
Failing (3.01-5.00)	0	0.0

Relationship between Parental Factors with Students' Self-Concept and Academic Performance

Correlational analysis was conducted using Spearman rho to determine if the parental factors described above were significantly related to the student's self-concept and academic performance (Table 4). It can be learned from the table that parental factors such as educational attainment ($r = .916, p < .05$) and school/classroom involvement ($r = .857, p < .05$) were significantly related to the student's self-concept. Similarly, the parent's educational attainment ($r = .883, p < .05$) and school/classroom involvement ($r = .792, p < .05$) were significantly related to the academic rating of the students. The correlation is also positive and strong, which implies that these factors can explain the self-beliefs and performances amidst the COVID-19 pandemic and distance learning.

In contrast, parental factors regarding the number of children, relationship status, and parents' monthly income were not significantly related ($p > .05$) to self-concept and academic performance. This could mean that these parental factors do not affect or influence the student's beliefs and achievements at school.

Table 4. Relationship between Parental Factors with Students' Self-Concept and Academic Performance

Parental Factors	Self-Concept		Academic Performance	
	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value
Number of Children	.136	.066	.105	.055
Relationship Status	.167	.051	.176	.051
Parents' Monthly Income	.093	.102	.143	.085
Parents' Educational Attainment	.916	.004	.883	.008
School/Classroom Involvement	.857	.032	.792	.043

Relationship between Students' Self-Concept and Academic Performance

The correlation between the self-concept of the student with their academic performance was determined (Table 5). The findings display a significant correlation between these variables ($r = .797$, $p < .05$). The correlation is also positive and robust, indicating that students with positive self-concepts have better academic performance than those with negative self-beliefs.

Table 5. Relationship between Students' Self-Concept and Academic Performance

Self-Concept	Academic Performance	
	r-value	p-value
School/Classroom Involvement	.797	.001

Discussion

Regardless of their profile (number of children, marital status, monthly income, educational attainment, and school/classroom involvement), the parents were able to support the higher education of their children, even with the difficulties of distance learning brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. This is similar to Agayon et al. (2022), Bacomo et al. (2022), Carbonilla et al. (2022), and Valoroso et al. (2022), where parents were seen to be more involved with their child's schooling amid the pandemic. The parents have shown resiliency despite the challenges while paying a premium on their children's education. This can be attributed to the student's positive self-concept and satisfactory academic performance. Irrespective of their background, parents can aid their children to boost their self-beliefs and academic upbringing in preparation for professional life upon finishing their college degrees.

The parents' educational attainment and school/classroom involvement were instrumental to students' self-concept and academic performance. Parental academic background and school engagement must be considered when dealing with the self-beliefs and scholastic achievement of the students. This supports the findings of Chohan and Khan (2010), Gonzalez-Pienda (2002), Martinez (2015), and Neuenschwander et al. (2007), where parental factors are related to the self-concept of the students with their academic performance. Further, the student's self-concept relates to their academic performance, agreeing with Gonzalez-Pienda (2002) and Sanchez and Roda (2003). Having helpful self-beliefs can help the students overcome distance learning and perform well academically. Optimistic students have shown maturity and were able to champion learning over the pandemic.

CONCLUSION

The study determined the parental factors related to the self-concept of the students with their academic performance. Parents are undoubtedly the primary teachers of their children, which was observed during the pandemic with the implementation of distance learning, be it online or modular. Some parental factors can influence even college students' self-beliefs and academic achievement. Thus, parents must support their children even if they are in their college years. Given that the student's performance was far from exemplary, it is necessary to provide remediation at home. Teachers must also review, revise, and enhance their learning materials to make them relevant for distance learning.

Since the study was limited to parental factors, it is suggested that future studies consider other elements related to the student's self-concept and academic achievement in distance learning, especially since regular face-to-face classes are not yet fully implemented. To expound on the relationship among the three variables considered, other researchers may discover the mediation or moderation effect of self-concept between parental influences and academic achievement in students.

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